

Rate and temperature dependent viscoelastic cohesive zone model for delamination of composites

*Ammasai Sengodan Ganapathi,
Giuliano Allegri and Stephen R. Hallett*

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Introduction

- Bilinear Cohesive Zone Models capture the interlaminar failure of composites well
- However, they are inadequate for loading rate and temperature-dependent fracture
- Traditionally, empirical expressions are used to include the strain rate effects¹ as

$$T_N(\dot{\epsilon}_N) = T_{refN} + T_{0N} \ln\left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_N}{\dot{\epsilon}_{ref}}\right)$$

$$G_{cN}(\dot{\epsilon}_N) = G_{refN} - G_{0N} \ln\left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_N}{\dot{\epsilon}_{ref}}\right)$$

Stiffness of the interfaces assumed as rate-independent

1. M. Lißner a , et al., Experimental characterisation and numerical modelling of the influence of bond-line thickness, loading rate, and deformation mode on the response of ductile adhesive interfaces , Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids , 2019.
2. Andrew Schlueter, An Experimental Study of Rate Effects on Mode I Delamination of Z-pinned Composite, PhD Thesis, Purdue University , 2012.

Fig: Typical Mode-I energy release rate for increasing wedge (opening) velocity of IM7/8552 ²

Loading rate and temperature dependent traction

A physically-based model that includes

- Strain rate effects at the interfaces due to QS/dynamic loading
- Viscoelastic behaviour of interfaces at extreme temperatures
- Viscoelastic behaviour due to thermoplastic toughening and extreme temperature and moisture

The loading part of the traction-separation curve is modelled by the

Generalized Maxwell model

$$\sigma(T, t) = \int_0^t E_0 \dot{\delta}(s) ds + \sum_{i=1}^N \int_0^t E_i \exp\left(-\frac{t-s}{\tau_i}\right) \dot{\delta}(s) ds$$

Using FDM forward scheme, we get

$$\sigma^{n+1} = \sigma_0^{n+1} + \sum_{i=1}^N \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_i}\right) \sigma_i^n + \frac{E_i \tau_i}{E_0 \Delta t} \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau_i}\right)\right) [\sigma_{i0}^{n+1} - \sigma_{0i}^n]$$

Traction-Separation curve

Loading rate and temperature dependent softening

From sub-microcrack formation theory, damage of a material can be represented as

$$D(T, t) = \frac{N(T, t)}{N_r} ; \text{ where } \begin{array}{l} D(T, t) = 0 \rightarrow \text{no damage} \\ D(T, t) = 1 \rightarrow \text{macrocrack} \end{array}$$

N_r -sub-microcrack concentration at rupture

Assuming a form for rate of damage

$$\frac{dD(T, t)}{dt} = (1 - D(T, t))^p A(T, t)$$

where the damage rate constant A is represented by the **Zhurkov's kinetic theory*** as

$$A(T, t) = \frac{1}{t_0} \exp((-U + \gamma\sigma(t))/(RT))$$

$$\frac{dD(T, t)}{dt} = (1 - D(T, t))^p \frac{1}{t_0} \exp((-U + \gamma\sigma(T, t))/(RT))$$

Using FDM forward scheme

$$D^{n+1} = D^n + \Delta t (1 - D^n)^p \frac{1}{t_0} \exp((-U + \gamma\sigma^n)/(RT))$$

Finally, the traction is updated as

$$\sigma(T, t) = (1 - D(T, t)) * \sigma(T, t)$$

Implemented as
material user
subroutine
ABAQUS /VUMAT

Model validation against Bilinear CZM – Mode I

Double cantilever Beam

Material - HTA6376/C *

Loading rate = 1 mm/S

$U = 114000 \text{ J/mol}$ and $\sigma_0 = 168 \text{ MPa}$

$E_1 = 100000 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and $E_2 = 1000 \text{ N/mm}^2$

$\tau = 6 \text{ S}$ and $p = -2.85$

*Paul W. Harper, Stephen R. Hallett, Cohesive zone length in numerical simulations of composite delamination, Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 2008

Proposed model capability – Mode I - DCB

Effect of loading rate

- Critical energy kept constant
- Peak traction increases with loading rate

Effect of Temperature

- Critical energy assumed to be constant
- Peak traction decreases as temp. increases

Fibre bridging effects

Effective damage rate constant

$$A(t, T)_{eff} = \frac{A(t, T)_M}{1 + \exp[C(D(T, t) - DC)]}$$

DC is Damage index at fibre bridging initiation

Model validation against Bilinear CZM – Mode II

End Notch Flexure

Material - HTA6376/C *

Loading rate = 1 mm/S

$U = 124000 \text{ J/mol}$ and $\sigma_0 = 230 \text{ MPa}$

$E_1 = 100000 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and $E_2 = 1000 \text{ N/mm}^2$

$\tau = 6 \text{ S}$ and $p = -2.9$

*Paul W. Harper, Stephen R. Hallett, Cohesive zone length in numerical simulations of composite delamination, Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 2008

Mixed-mode viscoelastic CZM model

Mixed-mode traction

$$\sigma_m(T, t) = (1 - D_m(T, t)) * \sigma_m(T, t)$$

Updated damage function

$$\frac{dD_i(T, t)}{dt} = (1 - D_m(T, t))^{p_i} A(T, t); \quad i = I, II$$

Updated traction function

$$\sigma_i(T, t) = (1 - D_i(T, t)) * \sigma_i(T, t)$$

Energy based mixed-mode damage

$$G_{mi} = G_{mC} - \int_0^{\delta} \sigma_{mi} d\delta$$

$$G_{mi} = G_{mC} - \left(\int_0^{\delta_{mi}} (1 - D_m) k \delta d\delta + \int_{\delta_{mi}}^{\delta} (1 - D_m) k \delta d\delta \right)$$

$$D_m = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{G_{mi}}{G_{mC}} \right) \left(\frac{\delta_{m0}}{\delta_m} \right)$$

Mixed-mode viscoelastic CZM model

Fixed Ratio M-mode, **GI/GII=1.33**, HTA6376

Validation - a carbon/epoxy material – DCB-Mode-I

Effect of Temperature

Effect of Loading Rate

Summary

- A viscoelastic Cohesive Zone Model (CZM) with loading rate and temperature dependent traction-separation is developed and implemented as a VUMAT subroutine
- The proposed model is compared against the bilinear CZM for mode-I and mode-II delamination cases
- An energy-based mixed-mode CZM framework is proposed and compared against bilinear CZM for a fixed ratio mode-mixity
- The VECZM model is validated for a carbon/epoxy laminate under mode-I delamination at different loading rates and temperatures
- The rate and temperature dependent simulation results are in good agreement with the experimental results

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Thank you

Email: gana.ammassaisengodan@bristol.ac.uk